

THE REACTIVITY OF 2-CHLORO-3 : 5-DINITRODIPHENYL

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2-Chloro-3 : 5-dinitrodiphenyl has been successfully condensed with sodioacetoacetic ester by directly heating the mixture of the two without any solvent giving 81% yield of the condensation product, thus disproving its reported non-reactivity by Bradsher and Amore. 2-Bromo- and 2-iodo-3 : 5-dinitrodiphenyl have also been prepared.

Bradsher and Amore (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **66**, 1283) reported their failure to condense 2-chloro-3 : 5-dinitrodiphenyl either with sodio-malonic or acetoacetic esters, the condensation being attempted by them in benzene, dioxane, benzene-xylene (1 : 1) and absolute methyl and ethyl alcohols. While the original compounds were recovered unchanged when dioxane, benzene or benzene-xylene (1 : 1) were used as a solvent, the corresponding alkoxy derivatives were formed when methyl or ethyl alcohols were used. This behaviour of 2-chloro-3 : 5-dinitrodiphenyl is unexpected because the chlorine atom in 2 : 4-dinitrochlorobenzene is known to be very reactive (Richter, *Ber.*, 1888, **21**, 2470; Reissert and Heller, *ibid.*, 1904, **37**, 4364; Borsche, *ibid.*, 1909, **42**, 601). The alleged inactivity of the chlorine atom in the corresponding diphenyl derivative was attributed by Bradsher (*loc. cit.*) to the steric influence of the large phenyl group in the *ortho* position to the chlorine atom, which prevented the bulky ester anion to approach the halogen atom but offered little hindrance to the relatively small alkoxide ion.

The above explanation does not appear plausible to the present authors as the chlorine atom in this diphenyl compound is known to react with aniline, phenylhydrazine (Borsche and Scholten, *Ber.*, 1917, **50**, 596) and piperidine (Bradsher and Amore, *loc. cit.*).

This was therefore repeated using absolute ether as a solvent. It is found that condensation between 2-chloro-3 : 5-dinitrodiphenyl and sodio-acetoacetic ester occurs, sodium chloride being separated, but the yield of the condensation product isolated is very poor (2-3% of theory). The separation of sodium halide reaches a maximum after refluxing for more than six to seven hours and does not increase appreciably even on very prolonged refluxing (up to 58 hours). It has been found that the use of twice the molecular proportion of sodio-acetoacetic ester (*cf.* Borsche, *Ber.*, 1909, **42**, 601) has a marked effect on the efficiency of the reaction and the isolation of the product offers less difficulty. The products in such condensations have been observed to take time in crystallisation.

In the hope of getting better yields 2-bromo- and 2-iodo-3 : 5-dinitrodiphenyl have been prepared and used in place of the corresponding chloro compound but the yield does not improve.

It was thought unnecessary to use any solvent at all in a condensation of this type, particularly when a substance melts at a temperature reasonably below the temperature at which the sodium derivative of acetoacetic ester is likely to decompose. This modification enables the reaction to be carried out at a much higher temperature than the boiling point of ether and also avoids the diluting effect of the solvent, if any.

This modification in the method gives very good results and 3 : 5-dinitrodiphenyl-2-acetoacetic ester is obtained in 81% yield. The direct condensation, without any solvent, of a reactive halide with the sodium derivative of acetoacetic ester does not appear to have been previously reported and the present authors are of the opinion that it can be advantageously employed in a variety of similar condensations.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Chloro-3 : 5-dinitrodiphenyl was prepared by the present authors from 3 : 5-dinitrodiphenyl-2-amine sulphate by the method of Bradsher and Amore (*loc. cit.*). In the preparation of 2-*p*-toluene sulphonamidodiphenyl required as an intermediate compound for preparing the corresponding halides, the authors essentially used the method described by Bell (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2270). Either pyridine (*cf.* Case, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 119) or sodium carbonate can be used as a condensing agent in the preparation of this *p*-toluene sulphonamide, giving almost theoretical yields. It was also found necessary to use only half the amount of glacial acetic acid used by Bell (*loc. cit.*) for dissolving the 2-*p*-toluene sulphonamidodiphenyl prior to its nitration to 3 : 5-dinitro-2-(*p*-toluene sulphonamido)-diphenyl by fuming nitric acid and acetic acid (1 : 1).

2-Bromo-3 : 5-dinitrodiphenyl.—3 : 5-Dinitrodiphenyl-2-amine sulphate (5g.), prepared as described by Bradsher (*loc. cit.*), was diazotised by dissolving it in 8 c.c. of nitrosyl-sulphuric acid at room temperature with mechanical stirring for 2 hours. The resulting solution of the diazonium compound was slowly added to an ice-cooled solution of cuprous bromide (in 5 c.c. hydrobromic acid of sp. gr. 1.49) obtained from 2.5 g. of copper sulphate. The stirring was continued for 1 hour more and the yellow solid filtered at the pump and subsequently decomposed by warming with water on a water-bath till no more nitrogen was evolved. The solid was then filtered, washed with a very dilute solution of caustic soda and crystallised from alcohol to give shining yellow crystals, m.p. 110-11°, yield 3.5 g. (Found : N, 8.68. $C_{12}H_7O_4N_2$ Br requires N, 8.66 per cent).

2-Iodo-3 : 5-dinitrodiphenyl.—3 : 5-Dinitrodiphenyl-2-amine sulphate (10g.) was diazotised by dissolving it in 16 c.c. of nitrosylsulphuric acid as in the previous case. This was then treated with 10 g. of potassium iodide in 10 c.c. of water. The solid iodo compound was isolated as usual and crystallised from hot alcohol to give brownish yellow plates, m.p. 132-33°, yield 9 g. (Found : N, 7.67. $C_{12}H_7O_4N_2I$ requires N, 7.57 per cent).

3 : 5-Dinitrodiphenyl-2-acetoacetic Ester. (a) *Without the use of a solvent.*—Sodium (0.9 g., 0.04 mole) was reacted with ethyl acetoacetate (5.2 g., 0.04 mole) using anhydrous ether in a three-necked flask (250 c.c.) fitted with a dropping funnel, a reflux condenser and a mercury-sealed mechanical stirrer. The condenser was then quickly replaced by a calcium chloride tube and the ether was evaporated off, the dropping funnel removed and 2-chloro-3 : 5-dinitrodiphenyl (5.5 g., 0.02 mole) was quickly added and the mouth closed by a stopper. The contents were then heated for 4 hours with continuous stirring in an oil-bath at 100-10°. After 4 hours, the flask was cooled in ice, 100 c.c. of ether were added and the flask left overnight in the refrigerator. Next morning,

the red ethereal portion was decanted into a separating funnel and extracted four times with 50 c.c. lots of ice-cold 3% caustic soda. The paste left in the reaction flask was stirred with a cold 3% caustic soda solution till it completely dissolved. All the alkali extracts were combined and acidified with cold dilute nitric acid. A semi-solid brown mass separated. It was redissolved in cold caustic soda (3%) and the solution acidified with cold dilute nitric acid when a yellow fluffy mass was obtained, which on standing for 4 hours could be filtered. On crystallisation from a small quantity of alcohol it gave yellow crystals, m.p. 102-3°, yield 6 g. (Found : N, 7.53. $C_{13}H_{16}O_7N_2$ requires N, 7.53 per cent).

(b) *In anhydrous ether.*—A solution of 2-chloro-3:5-dinitrodiphenyl (2.7 g., 0.01 mole) in dry ether (80 c.c.) was added during the course of about 1 hour to the sodium derivative of acetoacetic ester in ether obtained from acetoacetic ester (2.6 g., 0.02 mole) and sodium (0.04 g., 0.02 mole). The mixture was refluxed for 24 hours. A clear red solution was obtained after refluxing for 2-3 hours. The contents were treated as described above, the final product being a yellow crystalline solid, m.p. 103° (mixed m.p. with the above condensation product), yield 2-3% of theory.

The condensation with the corresponding bromo and iodo compounds was carried out similarly in ether giving the same poor yields. Refluxing up to 58 hours did not increase the yield. The major portion of the halides could be recovered unchanged.

One of the authors (I. K. K.) is indebted to the Lucknow University for the award of a Fellowship.